

Is there a role for salivary detoxification enzymes in taste perception?

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Abstract

Flavour perception results from the interactions of many molecules in mouth, including the ones that occur between oral enzymes and odorants or tastants, which are released upon food mastication. Taste perception results from the activation of taste receptors present in the taste buds, which are bathed in saliva. As a result, molecules eliciting the taste modality have to be dissolved in saliva to reach the taste receptors and interact with salivary proteins. Some of these salivary proteins have a carrier role or a metabolization role via their enzymatic activity. Among these proteins are found some enzymes involved in the detoxification process. Interestingly, they can potentially recognize a large panel of molecules including taste molecules. The aim of this work was to characterise the presence of such enzymes in saliva, their ability to bind taste compounds and consequently to discuss their possible role in taste modulation.

Keywords: saliva, taste, detoxification, enzymes, glutathione transferases

Introduction

Taste perception results from the activation of taste receptors located in the taste buds on the tongue. These receptors bath in the saliva, which is involved in many processes including the solubilisation of taste molecules. Saliva contains many proteins among which some can interact with flavour molecules (e.g. lipocalins with fatty acids and hydrophobic molecules, proline-rich proteins with polyphenols, etc...) [1]. Using salivary proteomic analysis, differences in protein expression were correlated with cohorts of individuals differing in taste perception (e.g. carbonic anhydrases, cystatins) [2]. These observations support a direct or indirect link of these salivary proteins to taste perception and consequently their potential role in interindividual perception.

Among the 3000 salivary proteins identified [3], numerous enzymes were identified including enzymes ensuring the neutralization or detoxification of the reactive compounds. These enzymes include cytochrome P450, aldehyde and alcohol dehydrogenases and glutathione (GSH) transferases. Among the salivary glutathione transferases, the glutathione transferase GSTP1 seems the most expressed in saliva [4]. Diets rich in coffee or broccoli increase the salivary glutathione transferase activity, suggesting increased expression of this enzyme family [5].

In this study, we have identified two major detoxifying enzymes in the saliva of 32 people, namely glutathione transferases (GST) isoforms GSTA1 and GSTP1. In order to gain a deeper understanding of their binding potential, they were heterologously produced and purified. Then, we measured by an enzymatic screening assay their binding abilities toward taste compounds. Some bitter compounds strongly interacting with these enzymes were identified. To further characterise the molecular interactions, one X-ray structure of GSTA1 in complex with a bitter molecule was solved. These results shed light on the potential modulation of taste perception by glutathione transferases in saliva.

Experimental

Saliva collection and GST titration by ELISA

For this study, a cohort of 32 people participated to saliva collection. Among the people, information about birth date and gender were collected. Saliva was collected by stimulation. People were asked to chew a piece of Parafilm® laboratory film (American National Can, Chicago, IL, USA) during 5 min and to spit out saliva regularly before storage at -80°C until analysis. Before biochemical analysis, saliva samples were thawed and then centrifuged 15 min at 15 000 g. Analysis of all samples were done simultaneously. GSTA1 and GSTP1 were titrated following an ELISA protocol by using commercial kits (Abbeva, Cambridge, UK).

GST production, purification and enzymatic screening conditions

GSTA1 and GSTP1 genes were subcloned in pET22b vector (Novagen, Darmstadt, Germany) by gene synthesis and used for transformation of *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) strain (Novagen). Protein expression was performed as previously described [6] and purified on glutathione-sepharose affinity columns. For enzymatic tests, GSTs were dialyzed in potassium phosphate buffer 0.1 M pH 7.4. GSH-transferase reaction was followed spectrophotometrically at 340 nm by monitoring the absorbance of the glutathione conjugation product of chloro-dinitrobenzene (CDNB). In brief, a typical measurement consisted in 50 nM GST, 1 mM GSH, 1 mM CDNB and 10 μ M of pure bitter compound in 0.1 M potassium phosphate buffer pH 7.4.

X-ray crystallography

In order to obtain a high-resolution structure of GSTA1 in complex with a bitter compound, an X-ray crystallography approach was carried out. GSTA1 was crystallized by the hanging-drop method as previously described [6] and complex crystals were obtained by soaking preformed crystals with 10 mM hexyl-isothiocyanate and 10 mM GSH. Crystals were diffracted to 2.03 angstroms resolution on the beamline PX1 at the SOLEIL synchrotron (St-Aubin, France). Data processing was made following a procedure previously described [6].

Results and discussion

Evaluation of the level of glutathione transferases GSTA1 and GSTP1 in the saliva of 32 people

In a previous study, it was shown that glutathione transferase activity was present in human saliva [5] but the isoform inter-individual concentrations remain to be investigated. GSTs conjugate the glutathione (GSH) group to hydrophobic substrates but can also have a role of small molecule transporter. In this study, our objective was to investigate the inter-individual concentration of two glutathione transferases isoforms, GSTA1 and GSTP1, in a larger cohort of individuals. GSTA1 and GSTP1 concentrations were measured by ELISA assay on each saliva. A direct enzymatic measure was excluded due to the quick inactivation of GSTs activity on saliva samples due to the salivary hypothiocyanite [4]. The results show the presence of the two GSTs in all subjects. The mean concentrations are 10 ng/ml and 5 ng/ml of saliva for GSTP1 and GSTA1, respectively (Figure 1). Interindividual expression variations were observed, in particular for GSTP1 (one saliva contained up to 50 ng/ml of GSTP1).

Figure 1: Titration of salivary glutathione transferases GSTP1 (left box-plot) and GSTA1 (right box-plot) in the saliva of 32 people. Boxes represent interquartile range, middle horizontal lines represent medians, errors bars represent 1.5 times the interquartile range, red crosses represent mean values, black diamonds represent minimum and maximum values. Extreme values are indicated by empty circles and asterisks.

Screening of flavour compounds interacting with salivary GSTs

For *in vitro* molecular studies, GSTA1 and GSTP1 were heterologously overexpressed in *Escherichia coli*. High levels of pure proteins were obtained after purification. Previously an increase of salivary GSTs following specific diets such as rich in coffee or broccolis was observed [5]. These foods contain bitter tasting compounds. Thus, we settled a library of molecules with bitter taste properties. This library was screened by using an enzymatic inhibition test. For this test we used chloro-dinitrobenzene (CDNB), a substrate conjugated with glutathione (GSH) upon the transfer reaction catalysed by GSTs. Absorbance of the product GS-DNB at 340 nm enables to monitor the enzymatic reaction. Each flavour compound was added to the reaction mixture at 10 or 100 μ M, allowing to

assess its inhibition potential. The enzymatic inhibition resulting from the addition of the flavour molecule corresponds to the binding in the active site as a substrate, or to the binding in the active site, or in the ligandin site as a non-substrate binder. A good inhibitor means that strong interaction occurs with the GSTs, slowing down the conjugation reaction between GSH and CDNB. By using this method, we screened a library of about 40 bitter compounds of different chemical families namely flavonoids, isothiocyanates, heterosides, alkaloids and N-heterocycles (Figure 2). Two families of compounds showed good inhibition potential: flavonoids and isothiocyanates. This last family contains compounds that are known to be conjugated with GSH by GSTA1 and GSTP1. Hexyl-isothiocyanate inhibits near 50% of the GSH-transfer reaction of GSTA1. In order to have a three-dimensional view of the binding of hexyl-isothiocyanate to GSTA1, we used X-ray crystallography.

Figure 2: Bitter compounds screen using the inhibition test with CDNB as substrate. Compounds were screened at 10 μ M (blue bars, GSTA1; orange bars, GSTP1). CDNB and glutathione were used at 1 mM in 100 mM potassium phosphate buffer pH 7.0. Results are the mean of three independent measurements.

Interaction of hexyl-isothiocyanate with GSTA1 studied by X-ray crystallography

For the crystallographic study, we choose to deepen the interactions involving isothiocyanates as they were among the best inhibitors. Worth is to mention that isothiocyanates are inducer of glutathione transferases and also their substrates conjugated to glutathione upon catalysis. Crystals of complexes between GSTA1 and hexyl-isothiocyanate were prepared by the soaking method. X-ray diffraction images were collected at the SOLEIL synchrotron. Structural analysis revealed that hexyl-isothiocyanate is conjugated to glutathione and binds to GSTA1 active site (Figure 3). Both active sites of the GSTA1 dimer are occupied by the glutathione/hexyl-

isothiocyanate conjugates. Residues from the glutathione binding site interact with the glutathionyl group whereas residues from the helical domain that form the hydrophobic site interact with the hexyl-isothiocyanate group. Our results show that GSTA1 efficiently and tightly binds hexyl-isothiocyanate, enabling its conjugation to GSH. This process is likely quick in a physiological context such as saliva.

Figure 3: Structural view of hexyl-isothiocyanate metabolised by glutathione transferase GSTA1 deciphered by X-ray crystallography. Enzyme is shown as white cartoon, interacting residues are shown as green sticks, and hexyl-isothiocyanate is shown as orange sticks and spheres.

Conclusion

In this study we have quantified the presence of two detoxification enzymes namely GSTA1 and GSTP1 in the saliva of 32 people. Our results showed that GSTA1 and GSTP1 are recurrent enzymes of the salivary enzymatic arsenal of most people. By using an *in vitro* approach, we have shown that GSTA1 and GSTP1 are able to interact with numerous bitter compounds. Two families of compounds significantly inhibit the GSH-transferase activity, namely flavonoids and isothiocyanates. By using X-ray crystallography, we have shown that hexyl-isothiocyanate is metabolised by GSTA1 due to an active site efficiently adapted for the hydrophobic part of isothiocyanates. Isothiocyanates and flavonoids, as many other bitter compounds, are found in many plant foods and participate to the plant defence mechanisms. It is therefore not surprising that salivary detoxification enzymes act directly in saliva to reduce the toxicity of these exogenous molecules. Previously it was shown that specific diet rich in plant-derived foods such as coffee or broccoli increase the salivary GST activity, suggesting that the oral detoxification system is able to dynamically adapt to specific diet [5]. In two other studies, it was shown that GSTs participate to the termination of the odorant signal [7], and that several odorant molecules are metabolised by GSTs [6]. Salivary GSTs could have a similar role at the oral level by modulating the quantity of taste compounds reaching the taste receptors. In the future, studies aiming at detecting the levels of salivary GSTs in link with specific plant-based diets and in link with the taste perception thresholds of individuals for molecules specifically interacting with these enzymes should be addressed.

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